

**Delivering the next generation of open
Integrated Assessment MOdels for
Net-zero, sustainable Development**

D2.4 – Stakeholder-informed research questions

WP2 – Codesign

30/01/2024

Funded by
the European Union

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Grant Agreement Number	101081179		Acronym	DIAMOND
Full Title	Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development			
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02			
Funding scheme	HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Action			
Start Date	December 2022	Duration	48 Months	
Project URL	http://www.climate-diamond.eu/			
EU Project Advisor	Silvia Vaghi			
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems - ICCS			
Deliverable	D2.4 – Stakeholder-informed research questions			
Work Package	WP2 – Codesign			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/01/2024	Actual	30/01/2024
Nature	Report	Dissemination	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology – ETH Zürich (ETH)			
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Keywords	co-design; transdisciplinary research; stakeholder engagement planning; joint problem framing			

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable serves as a guiding plan for executing the stakeholder engagement strategy to be conducted in the DIAMOND project. The document presents the work done to identify, prioritise, and plan outputs and activities that involve stakeholders. This will result in a more effective codesign process that the DIAMOND project has committed to.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The DIAMOND project undertakes a transdisciplinary (TD) approach to update, expand, open, and develop scenarios for six Integrated Assessment Models, with the aim of addressing net zero emissions and sustainable development. WP2: Codesign leads this TD approach, which is broken down into three multi-stage phases: i) mutual understanding; ii) knowledge co-production; and iii) model co-ownership. Deliverable D2.4 presents the results of the first two out of three stages in "*Phase 1: Toward Mutual Understanding*", which is based on the concept of "joint-problem framing" indicated by the TD scientific literature as the initial step within a fruitful stakeholder engagement plan. The aim and output of this phase is a set of stakeholder-informed research questions, which are co-created in three stages. Stage 1 is a familiarisation stage, aiming to find common ground among DIAMOND partners and their work. Stage 2 focuses on reaching mutual understanding of the goals and aims of the transdisciplinary approach to be implemented by DIAMOND partners. This Deliverable, D2.4, presents these two stages and concludes in actions falling under three themes. These themes include: (a) strengthening internal and external communities of practice, (b) focusing codesign activities, and (c) improving the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement. These outcomes will be picked up on in Stage 3, which commenced in January 2024 and will conclude Phase 1 of DIAMOND's codesign process with the output of a final set of stakeholder-informed research questions, to be presented in Deliverable D2.5 (update of this deliverable).

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report and the annexes serve as evidence of accomplishment.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and cocreate research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
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Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
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Executive Summary

Integrated assessment models (IAMs) are increasingly used to inform policy decisions towards net zero emissions, and recently towards several dimensions of sustainable development. However, IAMs are often met with scepticism, and non-modellers often think of IAMs as black boxes lacking stakeholder engagement and transparency. Participatory modelling aims to address these criticisms by involving stakeholders in the modelling process. To build further on this more inclusive modelling approach, transdisciplinary modelling aims to move beyond consultative approaches, onto codesigning and coproducing IAMs with stakeholders. Transdisciplinary (TD) research focuses on addressing real-world problems that require scholars from different disciplines and stakeholders to come together. Transdisciplinarity is also underpinned by openness and reflexivity in the process of coproducing and integrating knowledge toward effective solutions for real-world problems such as the goal of IAMs to inform policy decisions toward net zero emissions and sustainable development. As part of the DIAMOND project, WP2 “Codesign” leads the TD approach necessary to coproduce, co-own, and open six IAMs.

TD research follows three phases, as does DIAMOND’s codesign approach. Phase 1 (In DIAMOND, *Phase 1: Toward mutual understanding*) familiarises different groups with the individual mental models that define the problem space and then jointly frames the project boundaries. The second phase (*Phase 2: Toward model coproduction*) involves coproducing solution-oriented knowledge that addresses the problem framing defined in Phase 1. Finally, the third phase (*Phase 3: Toward model co-ownership*) integrates and applies the coproduced knowledge into societal and scientific practices. Reaching mutual understanding of the codesign process is a necessary first step to understand what DIAMOND aims to coproduce, with which stakeholders, and when in the project timeline. The output of Phase 1 is a set of stakeholder-informed research questions guiding the coproduction activities of Phase 2.

Phase 1 is divided into three stages and this deliverable presents the results from Stage 1 and 2, conducted between March and November 2023. Methods used in these two stages include seven in-person focus groups, two online workshops, and two surveys. The data was analysed using a situational and thematic analysis approach. Stage 1 focused on familiarising project partners with the DIAMOND’s ‘problem space’, outlining their perceptions of DIAMOND’s mission and opportunities; IAM gaps and limitations; and stakeholder engagement barriers and opportunities. It thus produced takeaway questions that we further explored in Stage 2.

Stage 2, in turn, focused on reaching mutual understanding within the consortium, exploring how partners envision Phase 2 co-production activities and clarifying DIAMOND partners’ understandings and expectations of the stakeholder engagement process. The output of the second stage was a set of coproduction activities under three criteria. First, strengthening the external and internal community of practice, to allow DIAMOND to share experiences and transfer tacit knowledge on coproducing knowledge toward improving IAMs. Second, achieving more effective stakeholder engagement to focus on developing a richer understanding of stakeholders, when to engage them, how to improve communication with them and how to achieve a heterogenous representation of stakeholders. Finally, we elaborated on where to focus coproduction activities during model development.

With these three criteria well framed, we create a rich set of information that will be used in Stage 3, when stakeholders will be engaged to cocreate stakeholder-informed research questions. By presenting the findings from this deliverable to a heterogeneous group of stakeholders in Stage 3, we will incorporate stakeholder perspectives and refine and adjust the coproduction activities to represent stakeholder perceptions through cocreated research questions. The coproduction activities will be designed as multi-stakeholder discussion groups, a flexible, tailor-made format catering to different needs of the codesign activity. The multi-stakeholder discussions and Foresight workshops will begin in *Phase 2: Toward knowledge coproduction* in May 2024.

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1 Introduction

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) play a crucial role informing policy decisions aimed at achieving net zero emissions and sustainable development (van Beek et al. 2020; Braunreiter et al. 2021), which is vital in addressing and mitigating climate change (Fankhauser et al. 2022). However, IAMs often encounter scepticism and criticism, primarily falling into two broad categories: i) concerns about the lack of transparency surrounding their methods, limitations, and assumptions (Royston et al. 2023); and ii) inadequate consideration of the inherent complexity and uncertainty of societal dynamics in their calculations (Beckage et al. 2020; Koasidis et al. 2023).

To address these criticisms and enhance the transparency and accuracy of models, an increasing number of modelling teams focusing on climate action are adopting interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and participatory approaches (Jäger et al. 2023; Bailie et al. 2023; Gooyert et al. 2022; Lehtiniemi and Paloniemi 2023; Wachsmuth et al. 2023). Transdisciplinary approaches become essential when diverse academic and non-academic actors collaborate to find effective solutions for real-world problems, such as combating climate change inter alia through net zero emissions goals (Lang et al. 2012; Hoffmann et al. 2017). While participatory modelling engages non-academic actors or stakeholders for feedback and validation of model assumptions, a transdisciplinary (TD) approach moves towards co-production of knowledge in science and policy (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman 2021; Nikas et al. 2020). Recognising that knowledge flows across communities, the TD approach ensures a policy-relevant yet impartial flow of comprehensive and comprehensible information for selected stakeholders.

Thus, the DIAMOND project—*delivering the next generation of open integrated assessment models towards net zero, sustainable development*—aims to update, upgrade, and expand six IAMs, using a TD approach, to better inform decision-making around climate change mitigation and the interplay with broader aspects of climate action and sustainable development. This TD approach establishes, operationalises, and manages a cocreation mechanism driving all model developments and scenario exercises in the project. This mechanism places actors from relevant stakeholder groups (scientists, policymakers, industries, citizens) at the project's core, fostering mutual understanding for coproducing and co-owning models and knowledge. Our TD approach follows three phases drawing from Lang et al. (2012)'s ideal typical TD conceptual model (see Figure 1 in Lang et al. (2012)). Accordingly, *Phase 1: Toward mutual understanding* is followed by a *Phase 2: Toward knowledge coproduction* starting in May 2024, and finally *Phase 3: Toward model co-ownership in 2025/26*, which integrates findings from Phases 1 and 2 and finalises the codesign process in the DIAMOND project.

Phase 1 involves reaching mutual understanding through a joint problem framing approach (Pearce and Ejderyan 2020). Joint problem framing is the process of collectively defining the problem space within DIAMOND, establishing a level of understanding and convergence of multiple perspectives to lay the foundation for the coproduction and co-ownership processes in Phases 2 and 3. The joint problem framing is broken down into three stages, elaborated in Section 2 of this deliverable, which reports on the outcomes of Stages 1 and 2, internally engaging project partners towards defining the project's mission, goals, opportunities, and barriers before involving stakeholders in cocreating DIAMOND's stakeholder-informed research questions that will guide model development and the scenario definition space.

This deliverable is structured in three sections and a conclusion. Section 2 presents the outline of the TD approach, highlights the importance of TD modelling, and elaborates on the joint problem framing approach and the methods used in Stages 1 and 2 of Phase 1. Sections 3 and 4 share the findings from Stages 1 and 2. Finally, the conclusion synthesises and prioritises the findings, outlining the next steps of the joint problem framing in Stage 3, commencing in February 2024.

2 From participatory to transdisciplinary modelling

While the definition of transdisciplinarity varies, we take on the understanding that transdisciplinary research is a process involving scientific and societal actors that collaborate to address complex societal problems towards better addressing solutions for sustainability challenges (Pohl et al. 2021; Lemos et al. 2018; Mauser et al. 2013; Polk 2014). Additionally, transdisciplinarity combines an interdisciplinary foundation with an openness to “new encounters, coproduction of knowledge and reflexivity” (Vienni-Baptista et al. 2023). A central feature of transdisciplinarity is collaborating with stakeholders with the aim of arriving at solutions sustained and supported in different worldviews, often referred to as *stakeholder engagement*. Thus, we define the term ‘stakeholder’ as any societal actor, expert or non-expert, that affects or is affected by the research mission and outcomes (Reed et al. 2009), who are not part of DIAMOND’s consortium. When referring to ‘engagement’, such activities can take on various forms depending on the task, e.g., defining research questions, and/or validating model results. Stakeholder engagement may happen in targeted meetings, while others may take the shape of large, open-format discussions. The different options for stakeholder engagement include informing, consulting, involving, collaborating with, and empowering stakeholders (Durham; Baker; et al, 2014).

Participatory modelling also implies plenty stakeholder engagement-related activities (van Vuuren et al. 2012; Salter et al. 2010). However, the level of involvement in participatory modelling so far has been limited, and stakeholders are often engaged to validate results and research questions and thus lack ownership over models (Braunreiter et al. 2021). Legitimacy and robustness of modelling outcomes is needed to build trust and ownership over modelling results and recommendations, aiding uptake of modelling results to inform important climate action policy (McGookin et al. 2021).

Through a TD modelling approach that is open and reflexive, DIAMOND pushes for models to be codesigned, coproduced and co-owned by the stakeholders as well as by DIAMOND partners. In the case of DIAMOND, the consortium has an added feature that imprints challenges but also opportunities to improve methods and tools for transdisciplinary modelling, i.e., the diversity and number of partners involved in the project. While this is a typical characteristic of Horizon Europe projects, we also acknowledge that investing time in a joint problem framing phase will guarantee a truthful and genuine co-designed output. A well-designed and facilitated TD approach gives actors the time and space to build trust and ownership through a deep understanding of different perspectives, and guarantee a more grounded societal impact to address net zero emissions and sustainable development (Jäger et al. 2023).

2.1 The transdisciplinary process

Transdisciplinary research follows three phases as defined by Lang et al (2012). The initial phase of a TD project is to internally familiarise team members with the different individual mental models that define the problem space and from that point jointly frame the project boundaries. In DIAMOND, we have acknowledged the importance of focusing inwards as a first step in phase one. With such a large and diverse consortium of researchers it is important to break down the initial phase, first familiarising with the consortium partners, and then approaching stakeholders to deepen this process. This first phase also involves understanding who the stakeholders are in the project, while formulating an initial stakeholder group that over time will adapt and grow. By focusing on building a common ground among partners, we ensure that in the next phase, we will approach a carefully considered group of stakeholders with a coherently defined project. This creates a solid foundation for collaboration with stakeholders where we can integrate their perspectives into the problem space, adjusting project boundaries to address their needs and concerns before moving into the second phase of the TD process. This deliverable focuses on this initial step of phase one, focusing on partners’ perspectives before integrating stakeholders into phase one. Once we approach stakeholders as the next step to phase one, we aim to produce a set of stakeholder-

informed research questions that guide phase two.

The second phase involves jointly producing solution-oriented knowledge that addresses the research questions defined in phase one with stakeholders. Finally, the third phase involves integrating and applying the coproduced knowledge into societal and scientific practices (ibid) to address the problem space that was jointly defined in phase 1. The TD process is also often conducted in iterative cycles and this phased process is not always linear (Wickson et al. 2006). For example, phase 2 may reveal new and unexplored territories of the problem space, which requires one to return to phase 1. As this deliverable focuses on phase 1 of the TD process, we elaborate on this process and the importance of reaching mutual understanding that we followed below.

2.2 Phase 1: Toward mutual understanding

In Task 2.2, *Phase 1: Toward Mutual Understanding*, we aim to develop an understanding of the problem space (Pearce and Ejderyan 2020) to navigate the complexity and uncertainty commonly present in IAMs and establish goals and strategies of codesigning modelling improvements and scenario definition space.

Contrary to the title “mutual understanding”, the aim of this phase it not to reach consensus around the set of problems to address, or which methods to follow in the codesign process. Rather, this phase focuses on bringing to the fore different perspectives and keep them alive under a common point of reference in relation to the stakeholder engagement in the Consortium (Bornemann and Christen 2020). As Bornemann and Christen (2020) point out, this process of understanding multiple perspectives enables the development of an “overall problem framework”, capturing and linking different context-specific understandings of the research focus. Such an approach allows for a more complex understanding of the problem space and thus may guide the solution space more sensitively. Below we elaborate on the approach that we have used to develop a mutual understanding of this “overall problem framework” in DIAMOND.

2.2.1 Joint problem framing

Phase 1: Toward mutual understanding includes three stages (Figure 1) and follows an approach referred to as “joint problem framing” (Lang et al. 2012; Pearce and Ejderyan 2019; Pachoud et al. 2023; Jahn et al. 2012; Bornemann and Christen 2020). Joint problem framing is a process where a group of people collaborating on a certain ‘real-world problem’ expose, share and explore relevant perspectives of a problem situation, thereby restructuring individual perceptions to determine jointly framed goals and criteria to create effective solution to the ‘real-world problem’ (Pachoud et al. 2023).

Within this process, Stages 1 and 2 are targeted towards reaching mutual understanding of the codesign process among DIAMOND partners, which is the focus of this deliverable. The importance of taking the time to adequately define the project mission, goals, opportunities, and barriers before stakeholder engagement takes place, has a proven positive impact on the outcomes of the co-design process (Durham et al. 2014). Undergoing a clear process in preparation of stakeholder engagement can crystallise the project mission and make explicit when the mission becomes unduly influenced by stakeholders (Mielke et al. 2016). This process also ensures that stakeholders receive well-presented information to collaborate on and respond to, since stakeholders often have limited time to participate and it is important to make the engagement process effective and efficient.

Phase 1 - Towards Mutual Understanding

Figure 1. The three stages of Task 2.2 “Toward Mutual Understanding”, each stage feeding into the next. The green indicates the stages that are complete and reported on in Deliverable 2.4.

Stage 1 familiarised partners with, and jointly defined, DIAMOND’s problem space (Pearce and Ejderyan 2020). Stage 2 focused on understanding stakeholder engagement through the partners’ perspectives using emerging themes from Stage 1 (Mielke et al. 2016; Reed et al. 2009; Durham et al. 2014) through takeaways in the form of transdisciplinary-oriented questions. The upcoming Stage 3 aims to achieve mutual understanding of the codesign process between DIAMOND stakeholders and DIAMOND partners, focusing on stakeholder engagement to incorporate stakeholder perspectives and adapt the results of Stages 1 and 2. The final output for Phase 1, and the result of reaching mutual understanding, is a final set of cocreated stakeholder-informed research questions that will guide the coproduction of model improvements and scenario definition space in *Phase 2: Toward model coproduction*.

2.3 Methodological approach to transdisciplinary modelling

To design and implement a transdisciplinary research process for codesign mechanisms that define requirements for new model capabilities and scenarios with stakeholders, our team conducts a multi-layered strategy combining knowledge from different methods and tools (Seawright 2016). The selection of methods is based on an initial inductive approach, where methods used in the first stage offer a broad and open format to ensure an inclusive environment for all participants. As we move into later stages of the codesign approach, more focused and deductive methods are used to clarify and refine results from the earlier stages of engagement (Azungah 2018). For the initial engagement with DIAMOND partners, we applied a qualitative strategy that is supported by dialogue-methods (McDonald et al. 2009) in workshop and focus group formats (Kitzinger 1995). Following these methods, we employed surveys and voting or validation sessions to refine and further clarify data.

Workshop¹ data was analysed using a thematic (Braun and Clarke 2012) and situational approach (Clarke et al.

¹ Workshop methods are presented in Section 2 for Stage 1 and Section 3 for Stage 2.

2018; Clarke 2003). The findings included in this deliverable are inscribed in ‘situational analysis’ (Clarke 2005), thus producing and combining different dynamic maps to obtain a ‘thick analysis’ of constituting practices and their cultural meanings. We use situational analysis to understand a system of key human and nonhuman elements of a “situation” and their interrelations, in this case the DIAMOND project. Table 1 offers a list of the methods and tools selected following this approach including the analysis approach.

Table 1. The rationale of qualitative methods and used to collect and analyse data in *Phase 1: Towards mutual understanding*.

Method	(In/de) ductive	Stage in which was used
Focus group method	Inductive	Stage 1: Initial phase of a research cycle
Dialogue method	Inductive	Stage 1: Initial phase of a research cycle
Alone-together brainstorming tool	Inductive	Stage 2: To clarify initial phase findings in the middle of a research cycle
Survey method	Deductive	Stage 2: To refine prioritise findings at the end of a research cycle
Voting and validation tool	Deductive	Stage 1 and 2: To refine prioritise findings at the end of a research cycle
Situational Analysis approach	Inductive	Stage 1 and 2: Mapping out data to understand the project situation and boundaries, and identify linkages
Thematic Analysis approach	Deductive	Stage 1 and 2: Studying the situational maps to identify dominant themes

Situational and Thematic analysis methods have underpinnings in Grounded Theory (Strauss and Corbin 1994) and seek to explore the multiplicity of perspectives and the processual nature of modelling improvements in DIAMOND, attending carefully to differences, complexities, and range of variation in the data, including discourse data and analyses (Clarke et al. 2015). In situational analysis, the situation of inquiry is empirically constructed through making three kinds of maps (situational, social worlds/arenas, and positional) and through doing analytic work with the maps and often updating the maps (throughout the project), to reflect one’s evolving analysis of the situation.

The first maps, situational maps, take on a post-modern approach of elucidating complexities (Clarke et al. 2003). From here, the often invisible is made visible, and through analysing maps, key themes can be identified and taken forward for further investigation (Clarke et al. 2018). Situational analysis follows three steps. Firstly, one draws out an abstract map of all the data collected, secondly, one begins to order the map into a working version, thirdly, one does a relational analysis with the situational map. When doing a relational analysis, themes, connections, and gaps begin to emerge. The different elements are coded, categorised, and grouped (Strauss and Corbin 1994). This type of map is initially made during the early design phase, gaining a tentative sense of important relations among dimensions of analysis (Clarke et al. 2015). Second, the social worlds/arenas maps lay out all the collective actors and the arena(s) of commitment within which they are engaged in ongoing discourses and negotiations. Such maps offer interpretations of the broader situation, taking up its social organisational, institutional, and discursive dimensions (ibid). Last, positional maps lay out the major positions taken, and controversy found in the problem space. They allow multiple positions and even contradictions to be articulated. As already proved in other cases (ibid; Fosket 2016; Gagnon et al. 2016) this method is also relevant for policy research, which is the focus of DIAMOND as well.

This deliverable focuses on the process and elements of the first situational maps elaborated in Task 2.1, following the transdisciplinary process detailed above. We provide detailed accounts of each type of workshop, the coding phase and analyses in the next sections elaborating on Stages 1 and 2.

Methods following *Phase 1: Towards mutual understanding* will be complemented in *Phase 2: Toward coproduction*

with the implementation of transdisciplinary methods that accompany and enrich the coproduction process. One such method is the multi-stakeholder discussion group, a flexible format that allows us to adjust the engagement format according to stakeholder needs, focus of each workshop and stage of the codesign process. Doing so allows exploring the multiplicity of perspectives on the topic and how models address concerns originating from the target groups, while attending carefully to differences, complexities, and range of variation in the data (Charmaz and Thornberg 2021). Our transdisciplinary process will also map actionable knowledge and ensure usability by relevant stakeholders through participatory validation and integration (Pohl et al. 2021) which takes place in *Phase 3: Towards co-ownership*, the final phase of the codesign process.

3 Stage 1: Familiarisation of DIAMOND’s problem space

Stage 1 focused on familiarising project partners with the ‘problem space’ (Pearce, Ejderyan, 2020) through individual visits by members of the ETH team to DIAMOND modelling groups involved in work package 3 (WP3). The findings of Stage 1 were further explored in Stage 2 workshops.

3.1 Methods

3.1.1 2.1.1 Data collection

Stage 1 was designed as in-person visits to the core IAM modelling² teams who are working to expand, update and open six emblematic IAMs. The workshops lasted two to three hours and had two to three participants representing their partner organisation working on one of the six IAMs in DIAMOND. In one exceptional case, a larger workshop was held with eight participants working on one of the six IAMs. The purpose of this workshop was to elaborate on some of the emerging themes from the previous workshops that required clarifying. In total 21 participants contributed to the Stage 1 workshops.

Using the ‘focus group’ methodology (Kitzinger 1995), information was collected on the participants’ perceptions of:

- DIAMOND’s mission and opportunities
- Gaps and limitations of IAMs
- IAM’s and stakeholder engagement
- Modelling team’s work related to DIAMOND’s mission

Twelve questions under the above four themes guided the workshop. Participants were given *alone-together* time to answer each question on cards (Figure 2). This was followed by a discussion where participants presented and elaborated on their answers to the question. Extensive notes were taken during this discussion that were used in the analysis.

2.1.2 Data analysis

Based on the notes and the cards from the workshops, we mapped the workshop data on the online whiteboarding platform, *Miro*, coding stickies grouped under the 12 questions (an extract of the codes is shown in Table 2). Here, an open coding approach (Braun and Clarke 2019) was used to allow key themes to emerge inductively. Once all six workshops were mapped and coded in *Miro*, data was consolidated, grouping together all the stickies from the workshops under the 12 questions. The consolidated data was then checked for consistency, recoding and merging similar codes. Following this, categories were developed around the codes (Table 3). The *Clusterize* function in *Miro* was used to build semi-automated situational maps (Clarke et al. 2018) as seen in Figure 3, showing the interlinkages (lines) between codes and hierarchies (circle size) of codes. Emerging themes were then highlighted using colour on the maps (line colour, sticky colour) also indicating thematic overlaps (background colour). Through an analysis of these maps, a summary of the main findings under each question was written and these summaries formed the basis of the Stage 2 workshops and are also presented in Section 3.

Table 2. Extract of Stage 1 code book generated through an open coding approach (Braun and Clarke 2019).

Stage 1 codes

² One (WP4) team developing modules was visited too.

D2.2 – Transdisciplinary joint problem framing: Toward mutual understanding

A	C	collaboration	D
acceptability	capacity building	common	data
access	carbon neutral	communication	decision-makers
accessible	CGE	community of practice	degrowth
adaptation	challenges	comparability	demand-side
aggregated	change	comparison	dependencies
assumptions	circular economy	complexity	detail
B	CLEWs-EU	conservative	diamond
behaviour	climate	consistency	different
benchmarks	climate change	contentious	digital
black box	climate models	coordination	disaggregated
boundaries	closed	coupling	disciplines
broad	code		document

Table 3. Extract of the categories under which codes are organised.

Academic	communication and collaboration	funding and resources
acceptability, feedback, usefulness of results	communication and engagement	IAM use
alignment or harmonisation	expectations, results	IAM aims, goals, needs, expectations
challenges	expertise in team and resources	methods, limitations, assumptions & uncertainty
climate change	Feasibility	

Figure 2. Workshop participants' cards from one of the in-person focus groups.

Figure 3. The semi-automated situational map, mapping out stickies (text removed for simplification and readability) of DIAMOND partners’ perceptions of the ‘real-world problems’ that define DIAMOND’s mission.

3.2 Findings

Stage 1: *Familiarisation* outlined project member perceptions around the 1) DIAMOND mission and opportunities; 2) gaps and limitations of IAMs; and 3) various facets of DIAMOND stakeholders. In this section, the main themes identified in the Stage 1 data analysis are summarised. Themes are emerging topics, shared areas of interest and/or concern among DIAMOND partners. The importance of such themes lies in the barriers and opportunities they reveal to achieve DIAMOND’s intention of codesigning model development, scenarios and opening models. Each theme finalises with a *takeaway question* section, with each question being shared with partners to validate them and plan accordingly to integrate them into their future activities. Next to the question, a blue circle indicates when a question was dealt with in the WP2 Stage 2 workshops, which constitutes the next section of this report.

3.2.1 Theme 1: Achieving DIAMOND’s mission

Despite the project’s multidimensional nature and fronts across the sustainability spectrum, participants in the workshops primarily associated DIAMOND’s mission with addressing climate change. They highlighted two critical aspects: enhancing our comprehension of climate change and its repercussions and offering strategies to both adapt to and mitigate its effects, which was deemed particularly significant. These strategies encompass supporting policymakers in implementing climate-oriented policies, especially those promoting sustainable resource utilisation. Workshop participants underscored the necessity of a deeper understanding of climate policy. Additionally, a specific mitigation approach highlighted was the transition toward achieving net-zero emissions. DIAMOND’s objective is to contribute to this transformation by refining its IAMs, focusing on transparency, accessibility, and better alignment with real-world conditions.

Takeaway question: How can DIAMOND partners familiarise with current climate policy to support climate decision-makers?

3.2.1.1 Climate change policies

Participants highlighted various organisational bodies and policies related to DIAMOND’s mission in combating climate change, spanning national, EU, and global levels. These policies were characterised by varying timeframes, addressing both immediate actions and long-term targets. Some participants emphasised the pivotal role of effective climate policies, stressing the importance of considering diverse societal groups and incentivising transformative changes that influence consumer preferences.

Figure 4. Organisations and policies mentioned by partners relevant to DIAMOND’s mission, with Nationally determined contributions (NDCs) being mentioned the most, indicated by the size of the circle.

Figure 4 illustrates the mentions of policies and organisations (indicated by circle size), showing their relationships across different scales (indicated by position of the circle along the global to national scale), with the ‘Nationally Determined Contributions’ from the United Nations Framework Convention being the most frequently mentioned. Participants observed that IAMs should bridge global issues to the local scale. To bolster their effectiveness in addressing policies, participants recommended integrating social sciences and humanities within IAMs to accurately represent diverse societies. They also stressed the importance of openness and transparency in IAMs, advocating for accessibility to both the modelling community and decision-makers for the adoption of these models.

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: *How can DIAMOND develop an understanding of which organizations (stakeholders) each of the six IAMs target and, at what scale they address policy, matching specific stakeholders to specific IAMs for more effective stakeholder engagement?*

3.2.1.2 Challenges to achieving DIAMOND's mission

Four areas were identified as challenges to achieving DIAMOND's mission of addressing climate change and are elaborated below. The first was reaching mutual understanding amongst partners, specifically because of different disciplines in the project and occasionally a lack of common language. Participants agreed that reaching mutual understanding takes time and openness from all partners, which is not always easy considering availability limitations.

Another area of challenges identified was the technical challenges to be overcome by the modelling teams, such as data availability for meaningful results, model complexity, representation, and simplification of real-world complexity, and adapting to changing dynamics in the real-world. Participants felt that soft linking to DIAMOND's modules could address some of these challenges, namely, representation and simplification of real-world complexity and adapting to changing dynamics in the real-world.

Related to our transdisciplinary strategy, achieving meaningful science-policy-society interlinkages is challenging, specifically, pursuing meaningful stakeholder engagement, including working with the right stakeholders and building trust. Producing impactful results for decision-makers is also challenging and relates back to the technical challenges of models. Politics, such as agendas and lack of transformative will from stakeholders also impact the science-policy interlinkages.

Higher level challenges that participants highlighted focused on creating new knowledge and methods; and the concepts of 'open' and 'transparent' are still perceived as complicated within the consortium. Dealing with intellectual property rights was an example of the challenges represented by opening up models. These are relevant themes for the upcoming stages of the TD approach.

Takeaway questions:

- *Is there willingness and openness among the DIAMOND partners to invest more time interacting between partners to reach mutual understanding?*
- *Can a data sharing protocol increase data availability within DIAMOND?*
- *How module soft links address technical challenges IAMs face?*
- *Which stakeholders are needed and missing, and how can we engage stakeholders to produce impactful results?*
- *What does 'open' mean for DIAMOND partners and the different models?*

3.2.2 Theme 2: Advancing IAMs to meet DIAMOND's mission

3.2.2.1 Gaps and limitations of IAMs

The gaps in IAMs that were identified by participants fell under four criteria. Firstly, representation of the real-world was identified as vital to address how models represent society (understanding acceptability through preference, behaviour, and fair transitions), and how to represent uncertainty such as ruptures, extremes, and alternative pathways. Scenarios were suggested as a way of addressing uncertainty.

Secondly, participants also felt that the level of detail (increased granularity, spatio-temporal resolution,

disaggregation, and GIS representation) of models was a gap in IAMs that needed to be addressed. Availability of data is a major limitation to this challenge. Third, coupling was described as both a technical challenge and an opportunity for models to become comparable, more rigorous and a way of addressing model boundaries. Aligning scenarios was suggested as a means to link models for effective comparison. Finally, communication and engagement were identified as gaps. Specifically, improved communication for policy impact at a local level, being transparent about model assumptions and uncertainties and developing an understanding of common terms used in the project.

When thinking about addressing the abovementioned gaps and challenges, two overarching limitations were mentioned. First, limited hardware and software capabilities could potentially restrict the level of complexity of models, and secondly, scarce resources such as data, could act as barriers to more detailed representations of different dimensions within models, consequently limiting potential outcomes. Trade-offs are made as a response to these limitations and are difficult to avoid, such as the scale of models (e.g., how detailed is the model granularity?); model coupling (e.g., which soft or hard links to pursue); and focus area or coverage of models (e.g., what does the model include or exclude?). Model coupling through soft-linking IAM models with sectoral models, however, also presented itself as a solution to model complexity but the type and degree of coupling is presented as a limitation in modelling.

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: *How can DIAMOND better communicate limitations and trade-offs of IAMs inside and outside DIAMOND?*

Explore the types and degree of model coupling more intensely as a consortium.

3.2.2.2 Opportunities to advance IAMs

Workshops participants presented some broad areas of opportunities within the DIAMOND project to address the abovementioned gaps and limitations in IAMs as presented below.

Team dynamics and expertise were by far the most prominent opportunities mentioned, where many felt that the expertise in coordination and modelling, combined with teams that have worked well together in past projects offer an opportunity to improve IAMs. Linking and integrating models offered the opportunity to advance the IAM space, specifically through linking or coupling the developed modules with the six core IAMs. Working with many models offered an opportunity to share knowledge and resources among models, build experience on other models, and compare different models for more robust results. It was also suggested to work within a common framework agreeing on scenarios, assumptions, stakeholder engagement, and goals of the analysis to make models more comparable. Stakeholder input featured as a smaller topic, but some felt that exploring different approaches to stakeholder engagement, could offer opportunities to improve model and scenario development. Some of these approaches include early and continuous engagement with stakeholders, engaging with a more heterogeneous group of stakeholders, and improving communication of model limitations with stakeholders to increase the models' robustness in representing reality.

Takeaway question: *How can partners leverage their expertise within DIAMOND and increase discussions to exploit model linkages, learn more about the different models to improve stakeholder engagement?*

3.2.3 Theme 3: Stakeholders' involvement in DIAMOND

3.2.3.1 Who are DIAMOND's stakeholders?

Heterogenous and inclusive stakeholder engagement was expressed as an overarching need, avoiding an unbalanced representation of actors, including anyone who is influenced by or influences climate change and adaptation to and mitigation of climate change. Workshop participants also expressed a need to increase engagement with civil society and NGOs, from all spheres, including climate sceptics, and climate NGO's. These actors can guide research questions and include aspects that may not have accounted for in scenario development. Finally, participants mentioned that the private sector is an important and largely missing stakeholder group who can inform modellers on technology developments as well as feasibility of policy adoption. Government and institutions are also important based on their role as decision-makers with major influence, but participants also pointed out that different levels of government (e.g., local authorities) should be engaged. Experts in IAMs were brought up as helpful to building a community of practice around IAM usage and development.

These guidelines are a useful tool to review gaps in the stakeholder database explored in Deliverable 2.1, 2.2 (due month 17) and 2.3 (due month 29).

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: *Could understanding stakeholder differences help to develop heterogeneity in stakeholder engagement and result in more robust and relevant IAM and scenario development?*

3.2.3.2 Stakeholder's role in DIAMOND

Throughout the workshops, participants mentioned ways in which stakeholders could contribute to the DIAMOND project. These were coded and collected under six areas of stakeholder input or contribution listed in the likely order of occurrence in the project timeframe:

1. **Build stakeholder capacity** around IAM methodology, thereby increasing trust and uptake.
2. **Focus research** through identifying stakeholder objectives and aligning expectations.
3. **Get technical input** on assumptions, trends, data, and modules.
4. **Scenario development**, formulating new scenarios, improving existing ones.
5. **Feedback on the model results**, what they need from the results, whether the results are feasible.
6. **Translate** results into policy recommendations or communicating results to the broader public.

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: *How can we categorise which stakeholders can contribute to the different stakeholder outputs or activities and when in the project timeline these roles are activated for more effective engagement and integration of stakeholder knowledge into IAM and scenario development?*

3.2.3.3 Challenges in stakeholder engagement

Participants expressed various challenges around stakeholder engagement. Integrating knowledge generated through stakeholder engagement also seemed challenging and timeous in tight project timelines.

A lack of understanding between some stakeholders and researchers is also a challenge in effective stakeholder engagement. Participants identified areas that a lack of understanding about the role or purpose of IAMs and IAM methodology, or simply put, how IAMs work is usually observed when communicating with stakeholders. In line with this, it was mentioned that stakeholders often misunderstand that IAMs do projections (scenarios) rather than predictions (forecasts), and the importance of understanding difference between the two was highlighted.

IAMs have several limitations such as the role of uncertainty in modelling, the assumptions IAMs make, and simplification, such as defining the model scope and boundaries, which is necessary due to the technical limitations

of modelling. Linked to the above-mentioned misunderstandings and inherent limitations of models, two issues emerge between stakeholders and IAMs. Firstly, stakeholders often have unclear and high expectations of IAMs, and secondly, a lack of trust and uptake of IAMs and their outputs can emerge from the stakeholders' side.

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: Which stakeholder groups experience the above challenges and how can we address these challenges to build trust, align expectations, and increase uptake of IAM results by stakeholders?

3.2.3.4 Effective stakeholder engagement

To address the challenges in stakeholder engagement, participants stressed that regular communication and interaction with stakeholders needs to happen early in the project. Participants identified different strategies for researchers in IAMs, thereby also relevant for DIAMOND, to communicate with stakeholders more effectively. They expressed the importance of seeing stakeholder engagement as an ongoing process and improving communication opportunities, such as creating a platform for asking questions and adapting communication approaches according to the stakeholder category was also mentioned.

Some suggestions were made to enhance trust and transparency, build stakeholder capacity, and align expectations with stakeholders to form a better understanding of IAMs. These suggestions included: presenting IAM methods to stakeholders through webinars; documenting model development in detail throughout the project that communicates limitations such as assumptions and technical limitations; and forming a strong community of practice to share such documentation and learn from others.

Taken to
Stage 2
workshops

Takeaway question: How can DIAMOND partners form a process to prioritise, action, and implement the above recommendations to develop more effective stakeholder engagement?

3.3 Moving from familiarisation to mutual understanding in DIAMOND

The process of familiarisation helped DIAMOND partners enter a reflexive practice and identify their own mental models related to the DIAMOND project. The outcome of this stage was to create a clear picture of DIAMOND's problem space before entering the next stage that involved understanding the codesign activities and process in more detail.

The highlighted takeaway questions listed in this section guided the next steps taken in Stage 2 with the aim of reaching mutual understanding of codesign within the DIAMOND consortium. Some of the questions were not immediately relevant and were not taken on board directly in the Stage 2 workshops, instead they will be dealt with later in the project, or directed to the relevant work packages. Decisions on what to include in the Stage 2 workshops were based on how to concretely plan codesign activities that will commence during Phase 2.

Along with these questions, a general and overarching focus on stakeholders in DIAMOND was planned for Stage 2. Many participants identified the importance of stakeholders in IAM development but there is a need for a more nuanced understanding of both stakeholders and the engagement process in order to plan for more effective codesign activities (Mielke et al. 2016; Reed et al. 2009; Durham et al. 2014). This includes understanding the distinct types of stakeholders, where in the project they can contribute and at what stage of the project. It is also important that missing or overlooked stakeholders are identified in this process, to ensure a more heterogenous stakeholder representation that accurately represents society for effective policy recommendations based on model results. The next section elaborates on Stage 2, which moves from familiarisation to mutual understanding of the codesign activities and process.

4 Stage 2: Mutual understanding within DIAMOND

Stage 2 focused on understanding codesign activities and outputs through the partners' perspectives using emerging themes from Stage 1. A set of online workshops was organised within the DIAMOND consortium to look at the intersection of the different themes presented in the Stage 1 findings and integrated them, focusing on:

- Prioritising Stage 1 takeaway questions.
- Understanding the differences between stakeholders.
- Matching stakeholders with the inputs/roles required.
- Addressing stakeholder challenges, different methods to improve stakeholder engagement and communication of different components of IAMs.

4.1 Methods

4.1.1 Data collection

The Stage 2 workshops took place online on 26 September and 3 October 2023 using the whiteboarding platform, Miro and Zoom video conferencing. DIAMOND partners voluntarily participated in the workshops. They were all asked to read a report of Stage 1 in preparation. The workshops lasted two hours and included 11 and 15 participants representing their partner organisation. In total 23 individuals participated, with three people taking part in both workshops. The workshop attendees spanned across all core DIAMOND activities.

The workshops consisted of a presentation of the TD approach; Stage 1 results; and stakeholder categories, which was followed by three activities. Some tools used in the online workshops were: alone-together brainstorming, voting, and having open discussions. Participants were also given a few minutes to vote which Stage 1 takeaway questions were most pertinent to them, helping guide next steps for the project's TD approach. Data was collected throughout the workshop using the whiteboarding tool Miro. The approach was aimed at allowing participants to have enough time to collect insights and discuss inputs in order to feed and enrich the understanding of each of the workshop activities.

The first activity focused on how to categorise stakeholders to better identify their perceived interest and influence in relation to DIAMOND's aims using an interest-influence matrix (based on Durham; Baker; et al, 2014). Here participants were asked to think of examples of stakeholders, categorise them, and place them on the matrix.

The aim of the exercise was to problematise the different stakeholder categories (the type of stakeholder, their input knowledge, the stage of involvement, the degree of interest/influence (for more details see Durham, Baker, et al (2014) explaining the influence-interest matrix) they have and the degree of involvement in the projects they may have), and to allow consortium partners to think about stakeholders in a more detailed and diverse manner in order to plan the next steps of stakeholder engagement in a targeted approach. The benefit of this exercise was to allow participants to think about which stakeholders they would need to engage with and on what tasks during the codesign process so that WP2 can plan effective codesign activities in Phase 2, inviting targeted groups of stakeholders.

The second activity *Codesign what with whom*, focused on increasing stakeholder engagement efficacy by understanding which different outputs can be codesigned with which different stakeholders and at what stage of the project. Activity 3: *Stakeholder relations*, focused on increasing the efficacy of stakeholder engagement by elaborating on different methodologies envisioned to engage with the different stakeholders on certain outputs and activities. In the closing session, participants simultaneously discussed and wrote sticky notes of action points they would like to see taken forward.

4.1.2 Data analysis

Based on the Miro stickies produced in the two online workshops, the data was consolidated, coded, and mapped on Miro. After the coding process, the codes were checked for consistency, recoding some stickies, and merging similar codes. For Stage 2, the codes were slightly more focused on emerging themes from Stage 1 and actionable details such as methods and degree of collaboration in the codesign activities (Table 4).

Table 4. Extract of Stage 2 codebook.

A	B	citizen reps
Activity 2	before	collaborate
Activity 3	behaviour	communication
acceptability	C	conference
after	capacity	consult
assumptions	challenges	

Understanding outputs and activities to be codesigned with stakeholders formed the bulk of the analysis and output for Stage 2. Under this topic, six situational maps were made, each representing a DIAMOND output or activity identified in the Stage 1 workshops, which requires stakeholder engagement namely: *building capacity, focusing research, technical input, scenarios, feedback on results* and *translating and communicating results*. In each situational map, coding categories (Table 5) fell under *stakeholder group, degree of engagement, method, when to engage* and *keywords used*. These maps revealed the interrelations between different methods, stakeholders, activities, and project timeline. The *Clusterize* function in Miro was used to build semi-automated situational maps (Clarke et al. 2018) showing the interlinkages (lines) between codes and hierarchies (circle size) of codes. Graph 1 shows the consolidated code use under the six different activities. The codes are grouped in categories that help define the approach to stakeholder engagement. Through an inductive analysis of these maps, a summary of the main findings under each of the six activities or outputs was written, as presented in Section 3.

Table 5. Stage 2 coding categories

Stage 2 coding categories		
Stakeholder group	Degree of engagement	Method
When to engage	Keywords	Building capacity
Focusing research	Input	Scenarios
Feedback	Translating and communicating	
		TOTAL CATEGORIES: 11

After the Stage 2 data analysis, the final step was to validate, prioritise and understand which work packages to involve in the action points identified in the workshops. DIAMOND partners were asked to complete a survey with action points presented in a randomised order, where they had to rank how important the action was, how easy the action was to implement and the degree of involvement of each work package in the action. Section 3.2 synthesises action points into three areas of focus: communities of practice, codesign focus, and stakeholder engagement.

Graph 1. Consolidated tags of Stage 2 workshop codes showing which stakeholder groups were most often mentioned, the dominant degree of engagement envisioned, the imagined method of engagement and when in the project this engagement should occur, and finally keywords used the in sticky notes.

4.2 Findings

This section presents the summarised findings identified in the data analysis grouped into three areas: (i) focus – communities of practice, (ii) stakeholder engagement and (iii) codesign focus. These three areas have been identified as areas of importance to ensure an effective codesign process. Building strong internal and external communities of practice aid in sharing experiences and tacit knowledge across projects, specifically, experiences of codesign processes. Planning stakeholder engagement activities well in advance, selecting and experimenting with effective methods of engagement and also ensuring a heterogenous representation of stakeholders is particularly important to the success of effectively coproducing model developments that represent society more accurately. Finally, framing the codesign focus, aids initial engagements with stakeholders, to effectively communicate DIAMOND’s expectations and in turn receive feedback and perceptions of those expectations from stakeholder, as well as incorporate stakeholder perceptions and expectations into the codesign focus.

4.2.1 Theme 1: Community of Practice

Community of Practice within the DIAMOND consortium

There was a significant demand for an external Community of Practice (CoP) but also for increased leverage of expertise within DIAMOND. In large-scale consortia like DIAMOND, it is important to leverage the expertise within the consortium and take the time to build a strong CoP internally (Wenger 2011). Growing the internal CoP can pave the way for a more effective formation of an external CoP by understanding who to reach out to, what modes of communication and exchange work well and what the priority for the CoP is. As a method of strengthening the internal CoP, different teams can host webinars on their work and expertise, with Q&A sessions so that DIAMOND partners can get well acquainted with one another and take advantage of the expertise within the consortium.

Two important topics have already been identified during the workshops that can be the focus of the first webinars. Firstly, the need for a data sharing protocol was highly prioritised by workshop participants, which could act as a recommendation for organising a meeting or webinar series focusing on this topic as part of the relevant development activities of the project, where DIAMOND partners can express their needs and concerns around data availability and sharing within the project.

Another activity highlighted by participants is to host a webinar that focuses on what “Open” means for each model, in other words, the degree of transparency and accessibility to the data and code models provide to the users based on software licenses and other potential restrictions. This topic came up in Stage 1 and again in Stage 2 workshops, making clear that different models have different opportunities and challenges to open up in different ways.

External Community of Practice

There were significant mentions of the importance of interacting with other modelers in a CoP. In the interest-influence matrix activity in the Stage 2 workshops, participants imagined collaborative and consulting styles of interactions in the CoP. As an initial step to building a CoP, WP2 will support a series of outward facing webinars that would introduce the DIAMOND project to modelers who may be interested in being part of a CoP. Priority should be given to DIAMOND’s sister projects and in accordance with the plan on collaboration and synergies.

4.2.2 Theme 2: More effective stakeholder engagement

Achieving more effective stakeholder engagement, represented by a heterogenous stakeholder group and successful acquisition and integration of stakeholder knowledge into model development is a high priority for the DIAMOND consortium. Three areas should be focused on to achieve more effective stakeholder engagement as presented below.

Effective engagement activities

Another area of priority that participants identified is to create more effective stakeholder engagement, including communication, heterogenous representation, and how to integrate stakeholder knowledge into the DIAMOND tasks. This deliverable is the first step of improving stakeholder engagement which effectively prepares for engagement by exploring focal codesign topics, different methods of engagement, and diverse types of stakeholders with DIAMOND partners before initiating contact. For example, the exercise of matching stakeholders to different tasks was dealt with in Stage 2 workshops, to learn where to engage which stakeholder, when and how, helping to plan for more effective stakeholder engagement.

Heterogeneity in stakeholder representation

Partners seek to have heterogenous stakeholders involved in DIAMOND. This can be achieved by reviewing the

stakeholder database and noting key stakeholders groups that are underrepresented and how to fill those gaps.

A core group that should be well represented was found to be civil society organisations to increase the models' accuracy in representing citizens, but it was also deemed crucial that citizens take part in decision-making in model and scenario developments. Here we envision that as part of the TD process, a citizen's advisory board could be formed to ensure that DIAMOND includes citizen perspectives in the model and scenario developments.

Communication and building capacity

Outreach to, and communication and dissemination with stakeholders were outlined as top priorities based on the perceptions of workshop participants. Top of the list for more effective engagement was found to be 'improved communication' that goes hand in hand with 'building stakeholder capacity to engage with codesigning IAMs'. Specifically, a priority for participants was to effectively communicate IAM methods, limitations, assumptions, and trade-offs to stakeholders, in a language and format that is easily accessible. Improving communication is also essential in building trust, aligning expectations, and thereby increasing uptake of model results. A webinar for non-modellers could be organised that presents these topics in an easy-to-digest format. Along with building capacity, these webinars also scope interest and capacity for longer term codesign activities with the DIAMOND consortium. From these webinars, stakeholders who offer ongoing collaboration can be identified, versus stakeholders who wish to be informed or consult on the project. Capacity should be built as soon as possible, before initiating stakeholder engagement activities and then throughout the project.

Additionally, content could be added to the DIAMOND website addressing the broader topic of the importance of communicating effectively with non-modelers, including the public and policymakers. Within the TD approach, more actions are envisaged to support partners in co-hosting a series of public events more specific to the limitations and trade-offs in DIAMOND's IAMs.

Another vital element of communication that was prioritised by participants was translating and communicating model results. To translate results into policy recommendations and communicate results to the broader public successfully, we need to do a scoping exercise of accessible communication, dissemination, and exploitation of modelling results to civil society. To aid finding such effective modes, DIAMOND can collaborate with stakeholders who are able to advise on the major barriers and opportunities to effective translation and communication of results into policy and digestible formats for non-modellers. This gap needs to be addressed well in advance to fully exploit the project results within the project timeframe. An accessible format also needs to be established to show DIAMOND's limitations and trade-offs to maximise the project impact while aligning expectations.

4.2.3 Theme 3: Codesign focus

Some areas of focus for activities and outputs involving stakeholders were identified in Stage 1 and 2. These four integral activities named below overlap with many of the tasks of the modelling teams and WPs dealing with scenario development. Highlighting these activities in the WP2 workshops, reinforces the planned work represented in the tasks and aids in exploring how WP2 will bring in stakeholders to contribute to these tasks.

To effectively conduct these activities, Stage 3 will consider forming a *Codesign Committee* of members internal and external to DIAMOND to discuss the codesign process, next steps in stakeholder engagement, concerns to address and course corrections, with the following formats identified by participants:

Focusing research

Participants indicated their preference to focus on research aligned with stakeholder objectives and expectations. This can be done by organising several multi-stakeholder workshops to consult targeted stakeholders, presenting the initial research questions in DIAMOND, and then receiving feedback from the invited stakeholders. This activity

should happen fairly soon in the codesign process once stakeholders have agreed to their involvement.

Getting technical input

Workshop participants also felt that getting technical input on assumptions, trends, data, and modules, was important, and modellers should meet internally to decide what input they need and from which stakeholders based on their planned model developments (see D3.1 and MS5). In this meeting, modellers will formulate “clear asks” for input from the relevant stakeholders. Following this, WP2 will tightly collaborate with partners in WP3 to invite relevant stakeholders to bilateral meetings, a survey, or a webinar and include the “clear ask” in the invite. This task will happen in Year 2, soon after deciding on the planned model developments and gaining consent for engagement from stakeholders from our stakeholder database, and from then onwards, modellers should continuously get technical input from the relevant stakeholders as and when needed.

Developing scenarios

Another key upcoming activity is related to scenario development, formulation new scenarios, and improvements, requiring planning to ensure adequate stakeholder engagement. The work package (WP5) focusing on scenario development began their tasks in December 2023 and a first step would be to host a kick-off meeting to discuss how WP2: Codesign results can inform their approach to scenario development.

Feedback on results

A final and integral activity related to model development is to get feedback on the model results in terms of what stakeholders need from the results and whether the results are feasible. In Year 2, as part of our approach a planning meeting will be organised with modellers in DIAMOND on how to systematically get feedback on model results from targeted stakeholders. In this meeting we should explore which methods (e.g., meetings, webinars) and which stakeholder composition (e.g., focused groups, mixed groups) would be the most effective format and plan when in the calendar these would take place.

5 Conclusion and next steps

Transdisciplinary modelling offers an opportunity to build upon participatory modelling, adding open and reflexive elements that codesigns and coproduces models, increasing relevance, model co-ownership and uptake of results into policy recommendations (Jäger et al. 2023), which is a core aim of the DIAMOND project.

This deliverable presented two of three stages of *Phase 1: Towards mutual understanding*. This reflexive and open process focused on familiarising partners with DIAMOND's 'problem space' and reach mutual understanding of the codesign process within the Consortium between March and November 2023. Stage 1 outlined project member perceptions around the DIAMOND mission and opportunities; gaps and limitations of IAMs; and stakeholder engagement barriers and opportunities. The output was a set of takeaway questions addressed to DIAMOND partners around how to increase the effectiveness of coproduction activities, including stakeholder engagement and interactions inside DIAMOND. These questions guided Stage 2 where project members planned for different codesign activities and how to involve stakeholders, clarifying DIAMOND partner understandings and expectations around societal actors. The output was a set of activities that aim to improve coproduction and the accompanying stakeholder engagement. These activities fall under three themes. Firstly, strengthening the external and internal community of practice allows DIAMOND to share experiences and transfer tacit knowledge on coproducing model development and scenario design. Secondly, focusing on developing a richer understanding of stakeholders, when to engage them, how to improve communication with them and how to achieve a heterogenous representation of stakeholders can achieve more effective stakeholder engagement. Finally, defining targets focus areas for coproduction activities in model and scenario development can aid in managing expectations and increasing uptake of models to inform policy.

The first two stages are a necessary and important step to codesign a set of research questions with stakeholders in Stage 3. Taking the time for this preparatory phase to reach mutual understanding within DIAMOND before engaging stakeholders builds a more solid foundation for the transdisciplinary process (Durham et al. 2014). Doing so before integrating stakeholder perspectives proves to be valuable by adequately preparing partners in approaching stakeholders in a well-organised, clearly defined manner (Mielke et al. 2016). It also allows partners to familiarise with diverse kinds of stakeholders, create a richer understanding of codesign processes, and shift their perceptions of how, when and where to involve which stakeholders in the project (Krütli et al. 2010; Durham, et al, 2014; Mielke, et al, 2016; Reed, et al, 2009). By doing this internal preparation phase, we provide a rich picture that allows stakeholders to contribute to and provide their own perceptions of the codesign process in DIAMOND more effectively. With this, the results from these two stages may change based on stakeholders' own perceptions, thereby also contributing to planning the codesign process and activities (Krütli et al. 2010). This will account for more informed, well-embedded and impactful outputs at the end of the project period.

The next step is Stage 3 of *Phase 1: Toward Mutual Understanding*, where we will use a functional dynamic approach (Krütli et al. 2010) to plan Phase 2's multi-stakeholder discussion groups, matching the methods for, and timing of stakeholder engagement with the types of stakeholders. First, we will interview experts in communication of IAMs to review the findings from this deliverable. Following this, DIAMOND partners will align the findings from the deliverable with the WP3, WP4 and WP5 tasks, assigning specific stakeholders to tasks. We will then contact those stakeholders, and present the findings to them for their feedback and refinement of the Phase 2 research focus. These steps will lead us to a set of well-defined stakeholder discussion groups. The multi-stakeholder discussions take on a flexible format, in-person or online, to create tailor-made engagement activities based on the type of action, stakeholders involved, and outputs envisioned.

The finalisation of Stage 3 in project month 30, will result in Deliverable 2.5 which builds on this Deliverable 2.4 and will include the stakeholder-informed research questions that will guide *Phase 2: Towards model coproduction*.

Annex 1: WP2 Gantt chart

Figure 5. Timeline and next steps of the transdisciplinary process

Annex 2. Results from planning stakeholder activities and outputs

Graph 2. Keywords from the output "building capacity" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

Graph 3. Keywords from the output/activity "focusing research" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

Graph 4. Keywords from the output/activity "input" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

Graph 5. Keywords from the output/activity "scenarios" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

Graph 6. Keywords from the output/activity "feedback on results" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

Graph 7. Keywords from the output/activity "translating and communicating" including specific stakeholder names mentioned.

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